

Teaching Using Virtualized IoT Devices

Abstract

Kinesthetic Learning Activities (KLAs) are immensely valuable in courses relating to Internet of Things (IoT) development. KLAs enhance understanding of software, hardware, and their integration through hands-on experimentation in a physical lab/classroom. However, the shift from in-person to online classrooms, over the past year, has raised concerns about the viability of KLA based teaching. In this paper, we recount lessons-learned, challenges, and opportunities in moving from physical to virtual IoT labs. This is based on our experiences of conducting three online programs: two workshops on *Pseudo-blockchains with Virtual Raspberry Pis* and a graduate course in *WSN development using TinyOS and Contiki*. We discuss aspects of Kinesthetic learning that can be leveraged in an online classroom and the best practices in teaching virtualized IoT development.

Introduction

The effectiveness of Kinesthetic Learning Activities (KLAs) for Computer Science education has been studied widely. In [1], the authors compared traditional lecture methods to KLAs for teaching Design and Analysis of Algorithms and Operating Systems in a classroom setup. Two groups of students were taught the 0/1 Knapsack problem and 4 scheduling algorithms - First-Come First-Served, Shortest Job First, Priority and Round Robin. One group was taught using traditional lecture methods and another using KLAs. The KLAs were designed to involve students in the learning process through physical exercises. The test scores and feedback on the surveys showed greater learning among students taught by the KLA method in both courses. The suitability of KLAs has also been discussed for other Computer Science courses such as Theory of Computation [2] and Distributed Algorithms [3] in a classroom setup. In courses relating to embedded programming, students learn best by performing hands-on Internet of Things (IoT) development in physical labs. The KLAs are designed to teach the proper use and integration of software and hardware tools. This enables the application of theory to practice. The activities also improve communication and collaborate among peers.

The move to online education over the past year, owing to the COVID-19 pandemic, has created several challenges for effective teaching. In [4], the authors conducted an observational study to identify issues that negatively influence online learning. About 70% of the students indicated lack of focus or Zoom fatigue after multiple online sessions using powerpoints. 55% of the students felt social disconnection with peers, while 64% experienced lack of engagement during online classes. Moreover, 60% of the students felt a lack of clear guidance and communication from the instructors. These results are alarming and stress the need to adapt KLAs from in-person classrooms to an online environment. This applies particularly to Computer Science courses such as IoT development, which are centered around hands-on learning activities in physical labs. Certain coding platforms have been designed in recent years that allow for the ease of experimentation in online labs. These platforms offer quick feedback, code-review, and

grading. These platforms have been shown to improve student's learning experience [5]. Although the online labs cannot afford physical engagement with hardware due to logistic challenges, they offer some detailed understanding of emulating hardware. Therefore, with slight modification to the course syllabus, online classrooms can provide several learning opportunities for kinesthetic learners. The activities may be designed to realize the same course objectives, while developing a slightly different skill set among students. KLAs are expected to help circumvent the issues concerning lack of focus and engagement.

In the past year, we conducted two online workshops on *Pseudo-blockchains with Virtual Raspberry Pis* at IEEE CCWC 2021 and IEEE World AI IoT Congress 2021. The aim of the workshops was to demonstrate the computation of pseudo-blockchains on Raspberry Pis. While the workshops were typically held in-person and made use of physical Raspberry Pis, the online workshops in 2021 were modified to make use of virtual Raspberry Pis running on QEMU virtual machines. The QEMU virtual machines were selected since they emulate ARM-based Raspberry Pis. We also taught an online graduate level course in *WSN development using TinyOS and Contiki* at Coventry University, UK, in Spring 2021. Typically designed for an in-person modality, the course aimed at hands-on programming of embedded systems using sensor devices such as TelosB and Firefly, which invited a range of challenges in working with physical hardware. In the online modality of the course a single physical machine, owned by the instructor, was set up with the required development environment and connected to several TelosB devices. Each student was provided access to a single device through a virtual machine session and ssh tunnelling.

Although the objectives and outcomes of the online programs were similar to their in-person offering in the past, the component knowledge and component integration skills developed were very different. Component knowledge is specialized knowledge to solve specific challenges [6]. For example, on physical IoT devices component knowledge refers to details and capabilities of the software systems, the hardware systems, and their integration. Quick and effective organization of component knowledge is a key learning outcome for in-person IoT workshops and courses. While component knowledge is itself not a key learning goal, the nature of virtual IoT workshops and classes changes the type of component knowledge. Virtual devices require more overlapping component knowledge of physical IoT devices. For example, component knowledge about physical IoT issues includes debugging WiFi issues, installing new hardware, and preventing short circuits. In the virtual case, component knowledge includes working with virtual emulators, setting up virtual networks, and setting up virtual environments. The differences in physical and virtual component knowledge led to development of slightly different skill sets.

In this paper, we present our experiences in virtualizing in-person IoT workshops and labs. We discuss the challenges and opportunities involved in conducting the online programs, and assess best practices. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: in the next section we describe the online programs, we then discuss the challenges, opportunities and best practices in the following section, and lastly present the conclusions.

Conducting virtualized IoT development programs

This section presents details of our online workshops and the course. We discuss the component knowledge acquired in each program, and highlight the differences from the respective in-person offerings.

A. Online IoT development workshops

In 2021, we conducted two online workshops on *Pseudo-blockchains with Virtual Raspberry Pis* in conjunction with IEEE CCWC 2021 and IEEE World AI IoT Congress. The objective of these workshops was to demonstrate the computation of pseudo-blockchains using virtualized Raspberry Pis. In doing so, we discussed the basic principles of distributed computing and taught programming for virtualized Raspberry Pis. The tools for the workshops included QEMU virtual machines supporting ARM Raspberry Pis for MacOS and Windows 10, and Python 3. The workshop was divided into three parts:

1. Installation and testing of QEMU virtual machines
2. Installation and testing of Raspberry Pi Raspbian images
3. Building basic blockchains with two virtualized Raspberry Pis.

Parts 1 and 2 were designed to set up virtualized Raspberry Pis. The installations typically took several hours and were expected to be completed asynchronously prior to the workshop. For the same, clear and concise component skills and component integration documents and videos were provided to the student cohort. We assumed early undergraduate level familiarity with computers. The materials were vetted thoroughly on both MacOS and Windows before distributing to the students. Note that such preparatory material was not distributed in the past in-person workshops.

The workshop itself was a synchronous session. In the past years, the workshop has been held in-person and allowed for KLAs that required participants to physically engage with both physical Raspberry Pis and software. The online workshops could not afford physical engagement with the hardware but they offered detailed understanding of emulating hardware. Accordingly, KLAs were designed to realize the same long-term goal of the workshop: demonstration of the use of IoT to simulate aspects of proof-of-work blockchains. However, the short-term goals differed for the in-person and virtual modalities. For instance, in the short-term, the in-person workshops had to contend with WiFi isolation to enable communication between physical Raspberry Pis, in addition to contending with the physical devices such as power supplies and SD cards that were used for long-term storage. On the other hand, the online workshops pointed-to and set up a series of downloads. These downloads allowed us to build and test pre-packaged systems that enabled communication of virtual Raspberry Pis on a virtual network, in addition to the installation and use of virtual machines. Such issues led to different learning experiences.

Other differences also came about between in-person and online workshops. The online workshops lack experimentation with physical devices and relies solely on emulated

environments. As a result, they do not allow students to explore how a software bug may damage the hardware. On the other hand, they provide several unique opportunities, through the use of virtual machines, that were otherwise difficult in in-person programs. For example, in the online workshops, it is possible to program two or more virtual Raspberry Pis (memory dependent). Physically adding another Raspberry Pi or two requires purchase of additional infrastructure and may not be economical for a large student cohort. Moreover, virtual hardware cannot be shorted, dropped, or otherwise physically damaged. Rebooting a VM image from scratch is easy and quick. These differences must be considered for the design of appropriate KLAs in online labs.

B. Online IoT development course

The graduate level course in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) development, conducted at Coventry University, UK, aims to equip students with the skill set to develop and deploy large-scale, intelligent WSN. The course combines lectures in fundamental and applied aspects of WSN with in-person labs that include KLAs to set up Linux-based environments and program embedded devices such as TelosB motes. The course provides the students a unique opportunity to gain a solid understanding and experience in WSN development through hands-on experimentation and anchor their research in this field. Upon successful completion of the course, the students are expected to:

1. Discuss latest trends in WSN development.
2. Discuss and demonstrate the development of physical sensing systems from conceptualization through to deployment.
3. Understand the challenges associated with deployment of WSN.

Typically, the students are provided with a Vagrant file at the start of the course. The Vagrant file enables them to install a Linux environment on their machines that can run the Contiki-NG development suite. During the setup phase, they receive extensive in-person support and documentation to navigate the environment. Upon completion of the installation, they receive physical TelosB motes to start programming.

In the online modality of the course, the students were provided with the same Vagrant file and were expected to set up the Linux environment on their local machines. To assist them in the installation, concise documentation and video tutorials were recorded and made available. Despite this, the students relied heavily on one-to-one calls and support sessions over Microsoft Teams for debugging set-up issues. As an alternative, each student was given access to a unique instance of a Linux Virtual Machine (VM) with pre-installed packages, which was hosted on a remote desktop. Due to logistical constraints, the TelosB motes were connected to the desktop hosted by the instructor. Each student could access one TelosB device through their instance of the virtual machine. A video feed of the device was also provided so that the on-board LEDs can be used for debugging. The feedback surveys at the end of the course indicated that the students preferred the use of VMs over setting up their own development environment.

Fig. 1 - Daily usage of the VM instances from the day it was made available to the students up until the submission date on the 15th day and throughout the live demonstrations

Such a setup also allowed us to monitor the cumulative hours per day the individual VM instances were logged into during the course of the semester as shown in fig. 1. As can be seen, the VM usage (i.e. per student activity) varies for each student and across all days. Significant activity was noted from day 1 to 15 during which the students developed and submitted their code. Post the submission day (i.e. day 15), a significant drop in activity was noted. This was because once the codes were submitted, the students were only required to access the online portal to set up demonstrations. Such monitoring of student activity allowed us to understand the usage pattern and identify students who did not engage in the course to potentially extend additional support. Although limited data was collected during the course, in the future we intend to gather more qualitative and quantitative data (using feedback surveys and network management tools) throughout the semester.

Similar to the online IoT workshops, the long-term learning outcomes of the course remained the same for the in-person and the online modality. The changes in the programming environment and logistics, however, warranted slight changes in the course syllabus and short-term objectives. The provision of VMs required a familiarity with the underlying principles of virtual machines, and an understanding of tunnelling using ssh to access the remote instances. For the same, detailed instructions were provided using documentation, pre-recorded videos and synchronous tutorial sessions. Moreover, video recordings were provided to get started with programming on the VMs, as well as enable remote access to the TelosB devices. Although the setting up phase took longer as compared to in-person labs, the students acquired additional skills. The additional documentation and video recordings also proved to be a useful resource for the students throughout the semester. Furthermore, the assessments for the course were adapted to accommodate the changes in the development environment. During in-person

assessments, the students were required to demo a program that allows for communication between two or more physical devices to the class. The students could observe each others' demos, and learn from their peers and faculty feedback. In the online labs, individual assessments were conducted for each student in half-hour sessions. The students were given remote access to two devices and were required to demo communication between them. This curbed their opportunity to learn from the other students. On the other hand, it allowed for a detailed assessment and debugging of their program by the faculty.

Discussion

In this section, we highlight the challenges and opportunities offered by virtualizing IoT development. We also apprise best practices in conducting such online workshops and labs based on our lessons learnt.

A. Challenges

Following are the key challenges that we experienced during the conduct of our programs:

1. *Teaching via online labs is an unexplored territory* - The COVID-19 pandemic called for an abrupt move to online teaching over the past year. While it provided an opportunity for the academic institutions to minimize interruptions in course delivery, it introduced several challenges in ensuring student engagement and efficient learning. Significant efforts must be made to (a) develop KLAs that circumvent the challenges of online teaching of IoT development (b) develop platforms and technologies that would help realize the modified KLAs (c) establish quality standards for accreditation of online workshops and courses.
2. *Online labs introduce new logistic challenges* - Online IoT labs rely heavily on good Internet connection, upto date systems, and platforms that enable hardware emulation. Through our experiences, we learnt that the majority of students experienced poor Internet connection, and had to spend several hours setting up the development environment. The use of VMs in such instances is extremely beneficial. It was also noted that certain platforms may require purchase of a license to access certain features. Procuring licenses and managing accounts for each student may not be economical. We preferred the use of open-source platforms.
3. *Online labs constrain student experience with real-world hardware challenges* - As discussed earlier, online labs typically do not make use of physical IoT devices. This eliminates the challenges associated with procurement of devices. The emulated hardware allows the students to understand the design specifications and constraints of a device. Virtual IoT systems also allow broad access to many versions of emulated systems. This adds breadth often now found in physical labs, but with constraints of emulated devices. However, it does not allow students to detect aspects of their program that may damage certain

components of the hardware. There may be added constraints from the emulated system not found in the physical system.

4. *Online labs lack the feeling of a community* - Our experiences suggest that online labs can support technologies to serve as good alternatives to in-person labs. However, the students lack opportunities and ways in which to interact and collaborate with peers. Online labs make it harder to understand peer attitudes or learn through their experiences. This has resulted in students feeling disconnected from the course and the class. Appropriate group activities must be designed to create a feeling of community in online labs.

B. Opportunities

As we tried to address the challenges brought about by conducting online labs, we observed certain unique opportunities provided by the online modality. These are discussed below.

1. *Ease of setting up and tearing down online labs* - Unlike other STEM disciplines that may require specialized laboratories, setting up online IoT (and in general Computer Science) labs is relatively simple. They require minimal physical infrastructure and cost, and can exploit existing cloud technologies. Therefore, designing KLAs for online IoT labs should be straightforward.
2. *Online labs abstract away unnecessary details and ease troubleshooting* - By providing access to VMs for IoT development, we can streamline the setting up phase and focus energy on the subject material that is relevant to the learning outcomes. This applies particularly to online workshops that are short-term. The uniformity of the development environment for all students makes it easier to isolate and troubleshoot errors. Moreover, it provides an opportunity for the students to gain insight into the working of VMs. The management of VM instances by the faculty also ensures a secure working environment for students.
3. *Online labs enhance the breadth and depth of experimentation* - Online labs offer flexibility to experiment with different software and emulated hardware. For instance, the online IoT labs provide an opportunity to work with different versions of the operating systems, a variety of emulated hardware, and make use of multiple virtual devices. Such flexibility is difficult to obtain with physical hardware without significant associated costs. As such, students could develop portable programs that are not constrained to a particular device and test them over multiple platforms.
4. *Online labs increase access and invite a wide array of learners* - By its very nature, the online labs are not constrained to a fixed location and can be accessed from anywhere. This allows for a flexible class size and students from varying education and work backgrounds. This offers a greater flexibility in course design with each iteration to cater to the varying needs of the students.

C. Best practices

Based on our experiences in conducting the above programs, we have laid down the following best practices to leverage the unique opportunities provided by virtualized environments.

1. *Use plug and play technologies* that require minimum installations in setting up software and hardware platforms. This may significantly reduce the hindrance in learning.
2. *Provide extensive preparatory and discussion material* throughout the course to ensure adequate support is available to the students. Video recordings of the experimentation and synchronous sessions are good resources to come back to for the students. Schedule periodic support sessions and assessments to avoid gaps in understanding.
3. *Adjust the curriculum* to modify the component and component integration skills that the students would acquire in a virtualized environment. Update the KLAs such that they can be realized in the online labs while realizing the course learning objectives.
4. *Be mindful of the challenges introduced by online learning.* Design activities that can enhance student engagement and reduce fatigue. Include group projects to incorporate the social component in learning and build an online community.
5. *Always follow up* to gather student feedback on the program and adapt for subsequent iterations. Encourage self-directed learning to allow the participants to continue to learn and grow.

Conclusions

KLAs have been shown to be effective in Computer Science education. Although a shift to online classes makes it difficult to interact with the students, it brings opportunities to re-design KLAs that better fit an online classroom. In this paper, we recounted our experience of conducting three online IoT development programs and the aspects of KLA that were used to enhance learning. While online programs constrain the use of physical devices, they provide a greater breadth and depth of experimentation on multiple technologies. We recommend certain best practices for conducting online IoT workshops to successfully achieve the learning objectives.

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